

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

Deliverable 5.2 – Project Website

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List of abbreviations used in this document

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

R&I: Research and Innovation

WB: Western Balkan

WP: Work Package

Executive Summary

This document represents a general overview on the official Website of the Project "Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans" 101059411 – GreenFORCE, implemented by a consortium of five partners and one affiliated partner, under the Horizon Europe call "HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-01" and with the European Research Executive Agency (REA) as the Granting Authority.

The project website informs on: the project partners and activities (all WPs); resources and methodologies; policy and societal communication. The site on the other hand, link to the twinning partners websites for local access and more resources on green transition, and to science repositories.

In this regard, this document provides a brief overview of the related task in the work package 5 (WP5), in the context of the overall project, and visually explains the main user interface of the Greenforce Website website.

1. Introduction and background of the project

1.1. The GreenFORCE project and Work Package 5

The GreenFORCE project aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia), as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to wider policy initiatives for the WB region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; will transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and will engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, making sure that research and research management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations.

Within GreenFORCE project, WP5, aims at setting up and using tools to share and communicate the newly established knowledge and engage the project partners with wider audiences in the WB, as to enable highest exploitation and sustainability of the capacities and research results developed in this initiative. The specific objectives of WP5 are:

- To publicly disseminate the activities and results of the project through a project website and social media.
- To promote the project and partners, enhance its visibility, domestically and internationally.
- To share the knowledge on green transition in WB with the societal actors.
- To ensure sustainability of project results and innovative collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

Task : Project website and media exposure- The project website is already in place by M4. The website informs on: the project partners and activities (all WPs); resources and methodologies; policy and societal communication. The site will link to the twinning partners websites for local access and more resources on green transition, and to science repositories. The Project Coordinator (PC) created and will maintain the website, but all partners will contribute with input proportionally to their engagement.

1.2. Project Website (D5.2)

The GreenFORCE project website is <https://greenforcetwinning.net/>, and is already launched online and open accessed to all.

2. Website Architecture

The website architecture was primarily developed during M1 and M2 of the project. It followed the Idea that the main landing page of the project, should clearly represent the project logo and tagline, it's main navigating tabs, as well as a slider, providing continuous information on activities related to the project (The sliding page is agreed to be changed at least once per month based on recent activities and news with regards to the implementation)

Navigating down the main page of the website the following information, were primaly designed to be presented:

Our Research

short description on the working package / milestones _____

learn more about the Research Plan

Research in ALBANIA

Research in NORTH MACEDONIA

Research in SERBIA

Research in MONTENEGRO

Research in BHC/ KOSOVO

RESULT and DELIVERABLES of the project

partner logo 1

partner logo 2

partner logo 3

partner logo 4

partner logo 5

partner logo 6

partner logos hyperlinked

In this section, the research activities of the project would take place, together with a continuing information with regards to results and deliverables of the project.

Twinning Partners Logos hyperlinked to the specific webpages of each partner are included in the main page as well

The footer of the webpage, was designed to clearly represn first of all the EU Logo & Disclaimer, together with tabs on quick access to project website main tabs, as well as a dedicated section on “Get in Touch”

In addition, in the footer of the website, the links to all social media of the GreenFORCE project are provided. The website, on the architectural aspect, is directly and automatically linked to all dedicated social media platforms, providing on time information to all.

Logo of the Project

Quick Links

Calendar of Events

Get in touch

facebook

insta

twitter

EU Logo & Disclaimer _____

2.1. Development of the website and final interface

The final developed interface of the project, in it's main page, is represented in the following images:

Project main landing page¹.

OUR PROJECT

GreenFORCE

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia), as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to wider policy initiatives for the WB region.

The project's objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; will transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and will engage in networking for sharing, crossfertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, making sure that research and research management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, co-creation with academia, civil society and policy-makers at the regional level.

Information on GreenFORCE project

Research information in all 5 WB countries will be presented here

¹ Four different information with regards to project activities and news will be published here. The main landing page will be updated frequently during the lifetime of the project.

Our Partners

Twinning Partners

The GreenFORCE objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organizations that will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning, will transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organizations and will engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level.

The 5 partner organizations are:

- Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development in Albania;
- University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia
- Center for Economic Analyses (CEA) in North Macedonia
- Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organization based in Sweden
- Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) in Italy
- Affiliated partner: Polis University, Tirana

The twinning partners are introduced in the main page

All partners logos are hyperlinked to their specific webpages

Project's Achievements

Results And Deliverables

GreenFORCE contributes to five wider impacts of the destination as a twinning project that makes use of a knowledge-creation and management cycle of actions to develop scientific research capacities and research management and administration skills for the primary benefit of three WB partner organizations but also for the benefit of the two EU partners.

1. Increased science and innovation capacities for all actors;
2. Higher participation success in Horizon Europe and more consortium leadership roles;
3. Strengthened role of the Higher Education sector in R&I;
4. Greater involvement of regional actors in R&I process;
5. Improved outreach to international scale for all actors

Discover More

The "Results and Deliverable" section in the main page, introduces the user with the projec's aims and workpackages.

Lastly on the main page, the GreenFORCE continous updates on the upcoming activities are presented

2.2. Main Website Tabs

In the primary phase of building up the architecture of the website, the following tabs were included:

dropdown menu for each of the main tab?

About the Project	Our Research	Papers & Publications	Learning Hub	Events	let's talk
Description of the project	Research topics	Policy Papers	SummerSchool	Conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contacts - recent news - tbd
Consortium & Partners	Research per country	Books	Teaching Exchange	Project's Periodical Meetings	
RAB	Stakeholders & Actors	Articles	Teaching Curriculas		
Key crosscutting issued	Relevant data & legislations	Research Plan	PhD Thesis		

The final interface, on the top of the website page the main Tabs are represented as in the following image:

Each of the main tabs represented in the main page, are clickable, and provided with a dropdown menu, providing the visitors with quick access to the interested area.

Other examples of dropdown menus as following:

2.3 Sub-Tabs and Website Content

Each of the GreenFORCE website sub-tabs in the dropdown menu, as presented above, are already functioning and provided with information. A quick information on each of the sub-tabs is provided as below

2.3.1 "The Project" Tab

The project tab provides all the information with regards to the GreenFORCE project, making it easier for the visitors to have a clear overview of the project's aim, intended achievements, expected results and deliverables, its consortium and partners, together with important notes on project's key crosscutting issues.

The following images, show how the interface in each of the tabs looks like

The screenshot shows the 'Results And Deliverables' page on the GreenFORCE website. The page includes a navigation menu with options like 'The Project', 'Our Research', 'Publications', 'Learning Hub', 'News', and 'Contact'. The main heading is 'Results And Deliverables'. Below this, there is a paragraph of text describing the project's goals and a section titled 'Project's List of Deliverables' which contains a table of deliverables categorized by Work Packages (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4). The table lists deliverable names, their corresponding work packages, and some descriptions.

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package
D1.1	Report on project management bodies	WP1	D3.6	Supervisors' report on these co-supervised	WP3
D1.2	1st Report on RAB meetings minutes and results	WP1	D3.7	Report on the 1st stand-alone teaching events (curricula + research results)	WP3
D1.3	2nd Report on RAB meetings minutes and results	WP1	D3.8	Report on the 2nd and 3rd stand-alone teaching events (curricula + research results)	WP3
D1.4	Report on IPR, critical risks and mitigation, and ethics	WP1	D4.1	Report on WB green transition conceptualisation	WP4
D1.5	Data Management Plan	WP1	D4.2	The regional mapping report	WP4
D1.6	Evaluation Scheme	WP1	D4.3	Comparative report on green transition governance challenges	WP4
D1.7	Evaluation on results and impact report pathways	WP1	D4.4	Data base of green transition practices and impacts in WB	WP4
D2.1	Shared Strategic Research Agenda	WP2	D4.5	Research Study Report 1	WP4
D2.2	Joint proposals submitted to funding organizations in the EU and WB	WP2	D4.6	Research Study Report 2	WP4
D2.3	Proposal for a WB regional partnership on green transition for the 2025-2027 period	WP2	D4.7	A monitoring framework for WB green transition	WP4

The "Result and Deliverables" window provides the visitors with the information on the project, as well as the complete table of the project's deliverables.

All open accessed deliverables will be published and can be easily viewed by clicking in each of them.

A short bio of each partner organisation of the GreenFORCE project is presented in the "Consortium & Partners" sub-tab

The 6 distinguished members of the GreenFORCE Research Advisory Board are presented here

The Key Crosscutting Issues sub-tab introduces the main key issues of the GreenFORCE project

2.3.2 "Our Research" Tab

Under Our Research Tab, in the "Research Topics" sub-tab all information with regards to the project's research topics in each of the specific countries will be published and continuously updated as the research develops

In the "Our Stakeholders & Actors" sub-tab, the quadruple helix approach of GreenFORCE project is presented, together with the update on the stakeholder's map the project's engagement of actors during the research

The public accessed data and legislations related to the research in each of the WB countries will be published in the "Data & Legislation" sub-tab. The information with regards to the Open Access repositories will be published here as well.

2.3.3 "Publications" Tab

All publications being drafted under the GreenFORCE project, will be accordingly published and easily downloaded/viewed in the "Publication" section of the website

2.3.4 "News" Tab

GreenFORCE news on activities will be periodically and on time published under this section. The subtab will also help feed the social media accounts of the project and will make it easier for the web viewers to keep track on the activities implemented under the project

2.3.4 "Learning Hub" Tab

The Sub-Tab on "Twinning Experience" will be publishing all information and news related to twinning activities and the learning experience of the WB partners under the project.

Under the Learning Hub, all information with regards to the teaching experiences, support to the PhD and Master Students as well as the information with regards to Academic Activities (Summer Schools, Conferences etc) will be presented under this Tab.

More specifically, the future participants on the Summer Schools or even conferences, will get the detailed information and procedures for applying for attendance under the "Summer Schools" sub-tab

All information here will be published in due time, and be managed by the partner responsible for the specific activity/event.

A dedicated window for all PhD and Master Students, pursuing the research on Green Transition, is built under the "Learning Hub".

All relevant information with regards to the progress on research for each student will be available under this "PhD and Master Thesis" section

2.3.5 "Contact" Tab

The "Contacts" Tab will make available for the website visitors to get in touch for more information on the project.

A dedicated e-mail address is provided here : info@greenforcetwinning.net

Besides, the web visitors could register their e-mail addresses for periodically receiving the project's newsletters periodically

3. Important Notes

The website footer is present in every window/ tab and sub tab of the website, and it clearly indicates the EU logo, together with it's diwsclaimer.

The GreenFORCE logo and tagline, together with it's official e-mail address are as well present in the footer.

Besides, the project's social media accounts are automatically linked with the website, and easily accessed through th website interface.

The screenshot shows the website footer layout. On the left is the Green FORCE logo with contact information: phone number +355 111 1111 and email info@greenforcetwinning.net. In the center is a 'Quick Links' section with buttons for Home, Our Research, and Contact Us, along with social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. On the right is a 'Connect With Us' section with a text input field for 'Your Email Address' and a 'Subscribe' button.

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The website builds upon the GreenFORCE branding package, and makes use only on it's graphic/ designed elements

All illustrative images (including photos, or graphics) are original. They are either specifically designed for the project or , in the case of photographs provided by the partner's own archive, creating no issues with regards to copyright.

Example of photos already used in the website

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